

Progressed by English: A Quest for Africanisation of Language Instruction in Limpopo Rural Public Schools

Moloto (Masehela), B. M., Hungwe, J.P., Tauatswala, T. T., Letsoalo, T. V.

Educational Foundations, College of Education, University of South Africa, 1Preller Street, Muckleneuck, Pretoria, 0003, Republic of South Africa.

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Abstract

This article focuses on the challenge of English as a language of instruction in relation to progressed learners in Limpopo province. In this regard, the language of teaching and learning is critical in the learning process because it can determine the learning success of learners. In other words, it can determine whether some learners progress or not. The researchers used a qualitative approach to collect data using semi-structured interviews with learners, teachers, parents, principals, and departmental officials in the rural areas of Limpopo. Investigations revealed that progressed learners and learners at risk are faced with several challenges at secondary schools. Deploying Africanisation as a theoretical framework, we argue that the hegemony of English as a language of instruction needs to be counteracted by the accommodation of local African languages in the learning process.

Keywords: African Languages, Progressed Learners, Rural Schools, South African Education, Success Rate

Introduction

The purpose of this study was to explore the nexus between English as a language of instruction and progression in Limpopo high schools in South Africa. This study was necessitated by the problematic issue of progressed learners in South Africa. In exploring the possible response towards Progression as a challenge for teaching and learning, we draw upon the discourse of Africanisation. Since the inception of democratic dispensation in 1994, South Africa has, among many other social objectives, endeavoured to expand and make education accessible to all learners without regard to race, language, region, and gender. It is in this vein that in a congratulatory note to the 2023 Matriculants, Angie Motshekga (2023), the Minister of Education, alluded to the fact that:

Over the past 30 years, the government has continuously and consistently implemented policies, programs, and interventions that clearly demonstrate an unwavering commitment to expand and enhance basic education through the implementation of social justice principles of access, equity, redress, inclusivity, quality, and efficiency.

One such notable intervention aimed at the expansion of and access to basic education is the 1996 Progression Learners Policy. While scholarly research on progressed learners in South Africa has predominantly focused on causative concerns such as learner performance, marginalization/stigmatisation, over-age learners, ill-discipline, and policy analysis,

(Dlamini, 2021, Mogale and Modipane, 2021, Mogale and Malatji, 2022), in this study, we sought to uncover the nexus between English as a language of instruction and learners' progression in Limpopo high schools of South Africa. The research was necessitated by the observation that there is limited research on the nexus between English as a language of instruction (hereafter referred to as English) and progression in South African high schools. There is, therefore, a need, as McKinley & Rose (2022) argue, to examine how well English language training programs can assist students in achieving their academic goals. Furthermore, there are no studies at present that propose and advance the notion of the Africanisation of the language of instruction as a possible mitigating factor against the hegemony of English within the auspices of Progression in South Africa. In fact, most studies are tailored around finding solutions towards improvement of English proficiency among learners. In this respect, this article is constituted of two interlinked objectives. Firstly, the article endeavours to contribute towards the discourse on mitigating the phenomenon of progressed learners in South Africa by exploring African languages as languages of instruction as an aspect of Africanisation. In this regard, the article dovetails with the observation made by Motala et al. (2009: 251) that claims, "A key challenge facing many countries in sub-Saharan Africa is to ensure that all children enrol and complete basic education of good quality". It is noteworthy to state that in the Limpopo's rural area in which this study was conducted, English is only used as the language of instruction in schools in a locality where Sepedi, as an African language, is the dominant spoken language. Secondly, in discussing the notion of Africanisation with regards to the possibilities of deploying African languages as languages of instruction, the article brings a unique paradigm to the discourse on progressed learners in South Africa. Fundamentally then, this article differentiates itself from similar research about progressed learners because of the interlink between English as a language of instruction and Africanisation within the purview of progressed learners in South Africa.

The guiding research question, therefore, is: *How does English as a language of instruction determine progression in Limpopo high schools?*

To appropriately respond to the guiding question, this article is divided into six interconnected sections. In the first section, we present a background which gives an overview of the social and educational landscape of Limpopo. The second section is a literature review in which we expound and situate the notion of Progression in the South African context. This exercise is imperative because there are varied meanings and objections to Progression in different countries. The third section provides a literature review which specifically focusses on English as a language within the historical and contemporary context in South Africa and beyond. The fourth section outlines Africanisation as an apparent indispensable discourse within the educational landscape. The fifth section discusses the methodology while, finally the sixth section is an exposition and discussion on the research findings.

Limpopo Province: Some Background

This article is contextualised within the Limpopo Province of South Africa. Limpopo is one of the nine provinces in South Africa, situated at the north end of the country, bordering Zimbabwe, Botswana, and Mozambique. Because of the historical legacy of apartheid, the province is considered one of the economically underdeveloped provinces with relatively

limited infrastructure and other social amenities (Madiba & Mabiletja (2008). In terms of social diversity, the rural side of the province is composed of Sepedi, Xitsonga, and Venda. In this regard, the study by Maja & Du Plessis (2023) explores the unique difficulties that Limpopo's rural schools encounter because of teaching in English as a medium of instruction. In this respect, rural schools in Limpopo are impeded with challenges such as limited teaching and learning material, classroom overcrowding, lack of sporting and recreational facilities, and the absence of libraries.

Ruiz (2020). draws attention to problems like the lack of resources in the English language, the shortage of teachers, and the cultural gap that exists between the curriculum and the backgrounds of the pupils. To address the demands of rural schools and advance inclusive education, Richards & Pun (2023) argue that there is a necessity of a contextually appropriate language policy and focused support mechanisms.

The South African Constitution of 1996 states that everyone has a right to a basic education, and everyone has the right to receive education in the official language of their choice in public educational institutions where that education is reasonably practicable” (Sailors et al., 2010).

Madiba & Mabiletja (2008) have conducted a study that explores the sociolinguistic effects of using English as the medium of teaching in schools in Limpopo. In addition to aggravating educational disparities and maintaining colonial legacies, they highlight the negative impacts of linguistic imperialism on indigenous languages and cultural heritage. In light of this, Siziba & Maseko (2024) promote the continuous development of the Africanisation of education by encouraging multilingualism and language revival initiatives, which will become attractive in empowering learners and the advancement of social justice.

English and Progression: A literature review

The main objective of this literature review section, with particular attention to Limpopo, is to sift through the current debates and discourses on language of instruction and progression in South Africa. This exercise is essential because this study is not isolated but falls within the broader scope of transformation and access to education in South Africa. Language of instruction has been a contested issue in South African education, tracing back to the apartheid era when the Afrikaans language was rejected by mainly Black African high school learners. However, unlike the Afrikaans language, which was an imposition, English has a global appeal and is touted as a necessary and perhaps indispensable language of instruction. There is a claim that although there are eleven official languages in South Africa, only English and Afrikaans have been ‘appropriately’ developed to function as languages of instruction (Ramoupi, 2014).

The implication is that African languages in South Africa, as is the case in most African countries, cannot properly function as languages of instruction. It is this claim that African languages do not have the capacity to express academic discourses both in lower and higher education, which has perpetuated the use of English, despite evidence that it disadvantages some learners (Posel et al., 2022; Xulu-Gama, 2022). It is pointed out that “in South Africa, the majority of children do not speak English as their first language but are required to undertake their final school-leaving examination in English” (Taylor and von Fintel, 2016:75).

In a country in which English is spoken as a first language by only two percent of the population, Xulu-Gama (2022) explains that learners find themselves in a difficult situation because English employs linguistic and cultural codes that they are not familiar with. According to Posel et al. (2022), English culturally alienates learners by excluding their experiences, worldviews, and value systems because it is not just an academic but a cultural custodian of English people. The paradox is that English is a second, third, or fourth language in some cases, which learners acquire in the classroom while they continue to socially interact in their African languages in the out-of-school environment. In Zimbabwe, Zambia, and Botswana, learners used to be punished if they were found to be conversing in languages other than English within the school premises.

In an attempt to militate against learner challenges of English, various initiatives have been put in place in South Africa. The 1996 South African Schools Act delegates responsibilities to school governing bodies and parents to exercise their rights by determining the medium of instruction for a particular school. Schools have the right to define the language policy for the school based on the languages or language used in the community (Wildsmith-Cromarty and Balfour, 2019). Furthermore, the Act encourages the implementation of multilingualism by using more than one language for teaching and learning. In the case of Limpopo, the use of 'mother tongue,' which is mostly African languages, is regarded as facilitating multilingualism in Limpopo's rural schools (Madima, 2023). English, however, as a medium of instruction, lowers performance and increases dropout rates of African children in Limpopo Province schools (Seanego, 2022).

It is further suggested by Phiri et al. (2024) that using students' native tongues as their primary language of instruction benefits their academic achievement, cultural legacy preservation, and cognitive development because learners are familiar with the language. A point to note is that "most schools offer mother-tongue instructions in the first three grades of school and then transition to English as the language of instruction in the fourth grade" (Taylor and von Fintel, 2016:75). However, the arrangement of using the local language from grades 1 to 3 is not compulsory, and as a result, there are schools that use English right from grade 1.

In the specific context of rural Limpopo, some studies have been conducted that relate to the challenges posed by English instruction. Sithole's (2019) research findings indicate that learners' academic performance is severely hampered by inadequate English proficiency, which also contributes to educational inequality in the sense that learners whose first language is English are in a more advantageous position than those who hold an African language as their first language. In some instances, Netshipise (2022) points out that English has led to misunderstanding, misery, and high drop-out rates of students. In the quest for a response to challenges posed by English as a language of instruction, Sithole (2019) suggests focused treatments like individualized instruction and language enrichment programs. In the same vein, Mafokwane's (2017) study refers to the difficulties that school administrators have when enforcing language standards in Limpopo's rural schools. The difficulties include, among others, socio-economic factors, parental involvement, family roles, poverty, teacher competency, availability of resources, and language barriers.

In considering the social diversity that characterises Limpopo province, it is advocated by Anis (2023) that there should be cooperative efforts among educators, communities, and legislators to create inclusive learning environments that support children's academic and linguistic growth as well as culturally sensitive language policies. However, forcing learners

to converse in English as a way of improving English proficiency should consider the contextual challenges teachers face while putting English-medium instruction into practice in Limpopo schools (Richards & Pun, 2023).

There are numerous challenges in rural Limpopo, such as poor teacher preparation, restricted availability of English language materials, and cultural mismatches between the curriculum and learners' experiences, values, and worldviews. For this reason, learners are not only disadvantaged but are also culturally displaced by the use of English. Consequently, forcing learners to learn English ignores the region's language diversity and cultural richness, which causes alienation and poor academic performance. The result is that learner and teacher proficiency in the medium of instruction largely influences academic success (Manyike & Lemmer, 2014).

Also to be noted is that South Africa is often ranked low in mathematics and science performance in public schools. Taylor and von Fintel (2016) explain that “the extent to which language factors contribute to low performance is not clear, given that language disadvantages are strongly correlated with other confounding factors such as historical disadvantage, socio-economic status, geographical location, the quality of school management, and the quality of teachers.

For conceptual purposes, progressed learners refers to “the progression from one grade to the next without meeting pass requirements in secondary schools” (Dlamini, 2021). The concept of progression is not unique to South Africa but is formally expressed in varied terms in other countries' educational sectors. For instance, in the United States of America, this is referred to as social promotion, while in Uganda and Cameroon, it is automatic promotion (Mogale and Malatji, 2022). In these countries and many others, progression is deployed with the primary objective of increasing access to education for all learners. However, the paradox is that while progression is a systematic negotiated success, progressed learners are considered low performers who struggle to move from one grade to the next. It is for this reason that both the policy and practicalities of progression have proved to be challenging to both the school authorities and learners.

In the context of the South African high school educational sector, Mogale & Modipane (2021) state that “... the Department of Education implemented the Progression policy to curb the rate at which learners were dropping out of school. Furthermore, this was a measure to “include” every learner within the schooling system.”. In 2023, a total of 49,866 progressed learners wrote the requisite seven subjects during the examination, with 22,688 passing, representing 45.5% of progressed learners who wrote all seven subjects during the examination. Ultimately, Dlamini (2021) claims that progression, or social promotion, is the process of moving a learner from one grade to the next grade even if the learner has not met the pass requirements of that grade in order for the learner to remain with his or her peers.”. This is opposed to grade retention, whereby learners are retained in grade so that they have more exposure and time to learn. Kolobe and Mihai (2023) note that the policy on progression, which was introduced in the Further Education and Training phase in 2013, categorically bars the repetition of a grade more than once within each of the four phases of basic education. The South African School Act of 1996 spells out how learners move from one grade to the next. In this instance, Kolobe and Mihai. (202:) note that it is categorically stated that:

A learner may not be retained twice in a phase, and an overage learner must be condoned to the next grade to be on par with his or her age peers. Even if a learner does not meet promotional requirements, he or she should be progressed to the next grade due to either age cohort or number of years in the phase.

Progression falls within the purview of access to schooling. Dube and Ndaba (2021) observe that most progressed learners perform badly in many subjects, especially science, mathematics, and technological subjects. However, some teachers lack the commitment to focus on struggling learners because of overcrowding and lack of digital tools, learners walking long distances to school, and chores at home, especially for the girl learner. Furthermore, to accommodate ‘struggling’ learners, there are instances in which assessment standards are compromised. Paradoxically, progressed learners are referred to as such, a term that connotes development and success, yet in their case it is systematic promotion through the progression policy introduced in 2011 by the Department of Education.

In conclusion, this literature review has discussed the conceptual basis of the theme, English and progression, which is the theme that this article focuses on as it relates to English as a language of instruction and the effect that it has on progressed learners in Limpopo public rural schools.

Discourse on Africanisation of Education

This article now turns attention to the discourse on the Africanisation of education. Firstly, as noted in the background section of this article, this study was situated in Limpopo, a province predominantly occupied by people whose first language is an African language such as Sepedi, Xitsonga, Tshivenda, and others. English and Afrikaans, which are non-African, are found mainly in the urban areas of the province. Clearly, South Africa, as Wildsmith-Cromarty and Balfour (2019: 297) claim, has a history of segregation and the privileging of English and Afrikaans as the only languages of teaching and learning beyond primary schools.”

Furthermore, Akinmolayan et al. (2024) highlight the significance of Africanization in educational settings, contending that there are serious problems with English being the primary language of instruction, especially in Limpopo schools. To better serve local populations, he proposes that the Africanisation of education entails integrating African cultural viewpoints and pedagogies in addition to incorporating indigenous language to better serve local communities. This is because African culture is a complex and dynamic element that has a significant impact on many facets of life, including education.

Secondly, since the 2015/2016 student protests in South Africa, Africanisation as one of the transformational discourses has become a dominant lens in critically responding to the realisation that there is Western epistemic hegemony across all levels of education. In this instance, the dominance of English as a language of instruction in Limpopo primary schools is an indicator of this hegemony. In this regard, Zeng & Yang (2024) explain that indigenous languages are marginalised, and cultural identities are threatened by the hegemony of English. As a result, they advocate for practices and policies that support the Africanisation of education, such as the creation of curricula that are culturally appropriate and the introduction of bilingual education.

Furthermore, other considerations to note are that this article uniquely draws from the discourse on Africanisation, which is often discussed from a higher education perspective (Hungwe and Mkhize, 2022), to the primary school level. The imperative embedded is that Africanisation is the incorporation, integration, formalisation, and legitimisation of African epistemologies as revealed particularly in indigenous knowledge systems, worldviews, experiences, and perspectives, as well as value, linguistic, and cultural orientations into the formal institutions of African society. Africanisation is, therefore, an antidote to the systematic and deliberate de-legitimization of African worldviews that occurred during the colonial era. It is a realisation, as Kangombe (2022) points out, that education in Africa is dominated by curricula, practices, values, and orientations from the Western world, which formally colonized the African continent. Consequently, the contentious issue of language of instruction in South African primary schools arises within the spectrum of Western educational hegemony, which was colonially instituted. Kangombe (2022) goes on to argue that it is strong when he points out that for Africanisation to bear the required fruits, it has to touch the mindset of learners, teaching and administrative staff, as well as the provincial and national structures of education. Africanisation is, therefore, one of the transformative initiatives aimed at prioritizing the African condition, experience, and needs and not just a protest or revolution against the Western educational stranglehold on Africa. Ultimately, as Agbaje (2023, 142) contends, “Africanisation is about changing the syllabus, the content of what is taught so that it reflects and takes into account the realities of local people.”

The curriculum should, therefore, be directed at solving societal problems and meeting societal needs, which, unlike the curriculum proposed by a Western educational perspective, deterministically depicts how things exist for us in addition to defining what is in the world around us. In so doing, a Western educational perspective suppresses alternative viewpoints, and this leads to what is commonly called epistemic injustice. Epistemic injustice, Agbaje (2023) argues, is a form of education dominated by Western forms of thinking, perspectives, and concepts, while suppressing and terminating alternative worldview beliefs. There is, therefore, an urgent need for curriculum reform that promotes indigenous knowledge systems in Africa to meet the needs of the African continent.

Methodology

A qualitative approach was deemed most appropriate for the study because it produces in-depth, rich, and detailed data from which to make claims (Clarke & Braun, 2013). Furthermore, the case study was found to be the most appropriate for this study, and a single case study design was adopted. In a case study, the data collection and analysis focus on one phenomenon that the researcher selects to understand in depth, regardless of the number of sites or participants for the study (James & Schumacher, 2006), as is the case with this study. The researcher used semi-structured, face-to-face, or interview guides with learners, teachers, parents, principals, and departmental officials in the rural areas of Limpopo.

Research Findings

- **English as performance impediment**

This study revealed that most learners who participated in the research failed examinations not because they do not know the answers, but because they either failed to understand the instructions or they failed to correctly express answers to the questions in the language of teaching and learning. This study revealed that English as a medium of teaching and learning has an impact on learner performance. Learners expressed that the usage of English as a language of instruction for mathematics, geography, life sciences, and physical sciences makes it difficult to grasp the concepts.

Research participant: *“I needs a Physical Science teacher who is going to work with me closer. I need someone who can study with me and teach me step by step, because the language used (English) is a challenge to me.”*

Research participant(s): *It’s better when I’m here, but somehow, we do not understand because the English is too high.*

English is a problem because it is not our language.

Research participant(s): *My challenge is Geography. I hear the teacher, but the way question paper is written confuses me, the English confuses me.*

Research participant(s): *Geography is a challenge for me.*

Researcher 1: *What language do teachers use to teach?*

Research participant(s): *English and Sepedi.*

Researcher 1: *If question papers were to be asked in Pedi, would you understand?*

Research participant(s): *Yes. “I think it’s better I was learning in Sepedi; I will not be a Progressed learner today.”*

Other learner spoke of the need for dictionary.

Appreciating teaching at the enrichment centers which takes place during school holidays one progressed learners suggested, *“It’s better when I’m here, but somehow we do not understand because the English is too high.”*

This clearly suggests how English as a medium of instruction has become a barrier towards learning for progressed learners.

One repeating learner alluded to the fact that as the teachers teach him, he “understand, but come test time it becomes difficult.” A progressed Geography learner also lamented, “I understand the teacher, but the way question paper is set confuses me, the English confuses me.”

The implication here is that learners fail to interpret instructions when writing their tests.

Code-switching

Code switching is the teaching and learning practice whereby there is a change of language of instruction to another for the purposes of explanation of concepts. In other words, this teaching method is applied when it is assessed that the language of instruction impedes teaching and learning. For instance, the study revealed that teachers change from English to Isipedi in instances where they assess that learners would understand better in Isipedi.

All in all, findings revealed that most learners fail examinations not because they do not know the answers, but because they either fail to understand the instructions or they fail to correctly express answers to the questions in the language of teaching and learning. Generally, learners experienced difficulties in mathematics, geography, life sciences, and physical sciences. They complained about the terminology that is used in physical sciences and mathematics.

The need for African language of instruction

The majority of learners reported that they have difficulty in understanding new vocabulary, terminology, and science concepts provided by physical sciences, geography, and mathematics. One repeating learner alluded to the fact that as the teachers teach him, he “understand, but come test time it becomes difficult to respond to questions.” A progressed Geography learner also lamented, “I understand the teacher, but the way question paper is set confuses me, the English confuses me.” The implication here is that learners fail to interpret instructions when writing their tests. Learners also reported that they did spend a lot of time struggling to understand the language before they could grasp the content.

Asked if they would pass tests if all question papers were to be asked in their native language, all learners indicated that they would, which further supports the fact that English as a medium of instruction can also be a barrier to some learners. Learners also argued that since not all of them would need to use English in their future jobs or lives, taking English as a language of learning and teaching is not an ideal solution to their academic endeavors. Most of the learners indicated that they needed assistance in understanding questions from past examination question papers and that they would ask assistance from their peers who better understood content than themselves. One progressed learner confessed that he will “*stop pretending as I understand and start asking questions.*” However, progressed learners also lamented, “Learners who seem to be understanding always pass nasty remarks when we try to ask the teacher to repeat or be slow in the teachings,” and that this embarrassed them.

One progressed learner suggested that he “needed someone who can study with me and teach me step by step, because the language used (English) is a challenge to me.” This is consistent with studies conducted in China between learners who do content subjects in English and those who do all subjects in their mother tongue. A study conducted by Floris (2014). revealed that the learners in schools that use English as a medium of instruction could not perform as well as the learners who do all subjects in the mother tongue, partly because the English of the former group of learners was not sufficiently developed to cope with the materials presented in their content subjects. Consequently, inadequate language proficiency on the side of both teachers and learners might also be the contributing factor towards poor performance when English is used as a medium of instruction to teach all content subjects.

Most progressed learners also admitted that they experienced desperation in their classroom as many textbooks, handouts, and PowerPoint slides provided were written in English, which was difficult for them to understand. Some progressed learners would, as a result, remain silent even when they did not understand, while others would resort to staying at the toilets during periods. Most learners interviewed also stated that they had difficulties in understanding the handouts and/or the textbooks assigned by the teachers. Participants, therefore, believed that learning in their native language would be easier and more likely for them to understand what was being taught. During the interviews, it became evident that some learners did not want to speak in English at all, even though the interviews were conducted in English. They used their native language to respond to the research questions. Asked why they were not responding in English, one progressed learner responded, “Because I am afraid of making mistakes; I do not want to be judged.” Repeating learners also

expressed how problematic it was for them to deliver oral presentations or to participate in group discussions conducted in English, as English was a problem for them.

One learner who also had difficulty in English as a medium of instruction suggested that “*if teachers can be supportive, it would be better.*” ‘Supportive’ in this context means that teachers should frequently do code-switching, that implies that teachers should switch to the mother tongue during their lesson presentations. Learners believe that if they learn a subject using their own language, they will be able to better understand the concepts delivered and in so doing will also pass the examinations. Learners also indicated that they would better understand when they are “*taught by fellow learners who understand the subject better,*” because they would probably teach them using the home language.

Recommendations: Towards Africanisation of language of instruction

South Africa is a multi-lingual country with eleven official languages, nine of which are African languages spoken by the majority of South Africans as their mother tongue or home language (Seethal, 2023). Chavez et al. (2023) argue that English is the dominant language of instruction, with local languages only used in the learning and teaching of African languages. Paradoxically, parents want their children to study in English because they regard it as an important language that can direct their children towards their career path and partially because of the perceived benefits to English proficiency in the labour market.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that there is a connection between English as a language of instruction and progression in the Limpopo rural public schools. The research findings noted the challenges of English as a language of instruction in relation to progressed learners in Limpopo and that the level of English proficiency in these schools may be an impediment to progressed learners. There was a necessity to find out how well English language training programs can assist students in achieving their academic goals. Investigations revealed that progressed learners and learners at risk are faced with several challenges at secondary schools. The hegemony of English as a language of instruction needs to be counteracted by the accommodation of local African languages in the learning process of Limpopo rural public schools. Therefore, there is a necessity to ensure the provision of a contextually appropriate language policy and focused support mechanisms in Limpopo rural public schools.

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